

Diet and SARS-Cov-2 Mortality Risk: A Retrospective Observational Study

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In the fall of 2021, based on a self-reported questionnaire, we asked 3,525 families across Iran about their diet and their COVID-19 disease in the past two years (and possibly COVID-19 mortality in that family). The results showed that some diets increased the risk of COVID-19 disease and death and some reduced it. The following is an example of these diets.

- Consumption of animal butter in cooking as one of the cooking oils
- Consumption of olive oil as one of the cooking oils
- Consumption of turmeric
- Consume black pepper, red pepper or bell pepper
- Consumption of honey
- Do not eat fish and other seafood weekly
- Do not use household water purifiers

Group 1: There were 3488 families that had at least one of the above items in their diet as usual.

Group 2: There were 37 families who did not have any of the above in their diet (complete non-compliance with the above diet)

The results show that the risk of reporting SARS-CoV-2 mortality in the second group was 4.2 times higher than the first group. **The two-tailed P value equals 0.0005.** By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be extremely statistically significant.